

Job Satisfaction on Organizational Performance in County Government of West Pokot

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199034>

Published Date: 31-July-2023

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to assess the effect of the job satisfaction on organizational performance in the county government of West Pokot. The study was guided by the following specific objective; to determine the effect of employee working condition on organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. The study employed the Locke's value theory and human capital theory. The study adopted descriptive research design. The target population of the study was the executive staff, supervisory staff and lower employees from the County government of West Pokot with a sample size of 100 respondents which was 10% of the target population as recommended by Mugenda and Mugenda (2003). Data collection instrument was structured questionnaires. The study used primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected using interviewer administered questionnaires while secondary data was obtained from scholars published journals. Pilot study was done in the Huduma centre of west Pokot to test the validity and reliability of the data collected instruments. The study adopted a multiple regression analysis to test the significance levels of one variable over another. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Data obtained was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 program. In conclusion basing on the findings, employee working condition ($\beta = .664$) was found to be positively related organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 1.551 and the p-value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that employee working condition has a significant effect on organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. The study came up with a number of recommendations. The study recommends that the management of county government of West Pokot should provide a healthy safe and conducive working condition to enable employees boost their moral towards the ultimate improvement of their productivity work towards the achievement of the organizational goals. The management of county government of West Pokot should seek guidance of terms and conditions to provide proper job and the assurance of its continuance in future as well as the absence of threatening factors and that short term employment results in: unscheduled turnover, low staff morale, and low productivity. The study was to be significant to the researchers, government bodies and to the human resource manager.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Working Condition, Employee Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employees are major assets of any organization (Armstrong 2013). The active role they play towards a company's success cannot be underestimated. As a result, equipping these unique assets through effective motivation becomes imperative in order to maximize the job performance. Also position them to take on the challenges of the today's competitive business

climate. Although extensive research has been conducted in the area of Human Resource Management, the same cannot be said on employee job satisfaction especially as it concerns developing countries.

Every organization seeks to attain a high level of performance, productivity and efficiency in their day to day operations and activities. To achieve these, organizations always set several goals and objectives, and always seek to attract and retain highly qualified and motivated workforce in order to effectively achieve these objectives. Organizations also try to create a pool of satisfied workforce to ensure that obstructions are not placed on the way of employees to generously commit themselves in the pursuit of stated and or emergent organizational goals. However, the total organizational performance depends on efficient and effective performance of individual employees who work in the organization. An organization therefore, look up to their Individual employee performance to gain high performance. This is because; individual employee's performance is an important factor that determines organization performance. When an employee feels satisfied about the job, he/she is motivated to put in greater effort in his/her job. This greater effort tends to increase the overall performance of the organization. In other words, a satisfied individual employee plus his effort and commitment are crucial for the success of the organization. In fact, no employee can truly be committed with his or her employing organization when he or she is not satisfied with her. Today, it is not easy to understand the effect of job satisfaction on work performance. Scholars have tried to establish the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance by delving into several research and studies.

Buchanan (2011) has noted that the two variables are positively related in a particular way when he posited that a happy worker is a good worker. On the other hand some researchers argue that the results are equally inconclusive with respect to the hypothesis that there is no such relationship. As a result of this ambiguity, this relationship continues to stimulate research, a re-examination of previous attempts (Buchanan, 2011). Job satisfaction is a mind boggling and multifaceted idea, which can mean various things to various individuals. Employment fulfillment is typically connected with inspiration, yet the idea of this relationship isn't clear. Of late, regard for work fulfillment has gotten all the more intently connected with more extensive ways to deal with improve work plan and work association, and the nature of workplace. Human relations approach tends to accept and argue that satisfaction leads to performance. An alternative view is that performance leads to satisfaction. However, a variety of studies suggest that research has found only a limited relationship between satisfaction and work output and offer scant comfort to those seeking to confirm that a satisfied worker is also a productive one. Labour turnover and absenteeism are commonly associated with dissatisfaction, but although there may be some correlation, there are many other possible factors. (Buchanan, 2011; Nwachukwu, 2006). Individual performance is a function of many factors: motivation, organizational support, the desire to do the job, ability, individual ability, and availability of needed information to do the job. All these are all within the control of a capable manager who needs to understand his subordinates and provide the much needed support and encouragement to them. Pushpakumari, (2008) note that satisfied worker works harder and better and put in more efforts that helps to improve organizational performance.

Accordingly, organizations try to create a satisfied workforce for the well-being of the organization. Thus the overall performance of organizations depends on the performance of individual employees in the organization. Because of this, organizations place a considerable reliance on their individual performance to gain improved productivity. Employee effort is an important factor that determines what an individual performance will be. In other words, a satisfied individual employee together with his effort and commitment are crucial for the success of any organization. Koys (2001) pointed out that it is crucial for an organization to understand what employee exactly feel, think on their job and stage of satisfaction, as this can help improve business outcome and is probably increased productivity as well. The success of any organization is a very important element of organizational survival. Every organization seeks to attain a high level of performance, productivity and efficiency in their day to day operations and activities. To achieve these, organizations always set several goals and objectives, and always seek to attract and retain highly qualified and motivated workforce in order to effectively achieve these objectives.

Organizations also try to create a pool of satisfied workforce to ensure that obstructions are not placed on the way of employees to generously commit themselves in the pursuit of stated and or emergent organizational goals. However, the total organizational performance depends on efficient and effective performance of individual employees who work in the organization. Organizations therefore, look up to their individual employee performance to gain high performance. This is because; individual employee's performance is an important factor that determines organization performance. When an employee feels satisfied about the job, he/she is motivated to put in greater effort in his/her job. This greater effort tends to

increase the overall performance of the organization. In other words, a satisfied individual employee plus his effort and commitment are crucial for the success of the organization. In fact, no employee can truly be committed with his or her employing organization when he or she is not satisfied with her. Today, it is not easy to understand the effect of job satisfaction on work performance. Scholars have tried to establish the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance by delving into several research and studies. Buchanan (2011) has noted that the two variables are positively related in a particular way when he posited that a happy worker is a good worker. On the other hand some researchers argue that the results are equally inconclusive with respect to the hypothesis that there is no such relationship. As a result of this ambiguity, this relationship continues to stimulate research, a re-examination of previous attempts (Buchanan, 2011).

Job satisfaction is a mind boggling and multifaceted idea, which can mean various things to various individuals. Employment fulfillment is typically connected with inspiration, yet the idea of this relationship isn't clear. Of late, regard for work fulfillment has gotten all the more intently connected with more extensive ways to deal with improve work plan and work association, and the nature of workplace. Nwachukwu, (2006) noticed that job satisfaction does not necessarily lead to improvement in performance. According to him, studies have however showed that job satisfaction connects adversely with increment in absenteeism, work turnover and poor resolve (Nwachukwu 2006). Human relations approach tends to accept and argue that satisfaction leads to performance. An alternative view is that performance leads to satisfaction. However, a variety of studies suggest that research has found only a limited relationship between satisfaction and work output and offer scent comfort to those seeking to confirm that a satisfied worker is also a productive one. Labour turnover and absenteeism are commonly associated with dissatisfaction, but although there may be some correlation, there are many other possible factors. (Buchanan, 2011; Nwachukwu, 2006).

Individual performance is a function of many factors: motivation, organizational support, the desire to do the job, ability, individual ability, and availability of needed information to do the job. All these are all within the control of a capable manager who needs to understand his subordinates and provide the much needed support and encouragement to them. Pushpakumari, (2008) note that satisfied worker works harder and better and put in more efforts that helps to improve organizational performance. Accordingly, organizations try to create a satisfied workforce for the well-being of the organization. Thus the overall performance of organizations depends on the performance of individual employees in the organization. Because of this, organizations place a considerable reliance on their individual performance to gain improved productivity. Employee effort is an important factor that determines what an individual performance will be. In other words, a satisfied individual employee together with his effort and commitment are crucial for the success of any organization. Koys (2001) pointed out that it is crucial for an organization to understand what employee exactly feel, think on their job and stage of satisfaction, as this can help improve business outcome and is probably increased productivity as well. Kingsley (2012) studied on the impact of office ergonomics on employee performance in Ghana National Petroleum Corporation (GNPC). The study aimed at finding out whether the workplace environment of GNPC had any impact on employees' performance. The results showed that deficiencies in office ergonomics affected the performance of employees by varying degrees ranging from 20-80 percent. Leblebici (2012) researched on the impact of workplace quality on employee productivity a case study of a foreign private bank in Turkey. The study was to establish the relationship between the work physical conditions and employee performance. Study showed that employees felt motivated while working in a modernized office, well decorated and well-arranged and with good storage facilities.

Job satisfaction is the total feeling likeness or dislikes that an individual has about his or her job. It is an effective or emotional response towards the various facets of one's job. It is an individual total attitude and perception towards one's job. Baridam and Nwibere (2008) defined job satisfaction as the degree to which an individual feels negatively or positively about the various facets of job tasks, the work setting, relationship with co-workers and the job itself. An individual with a significant level of job satisfaction holds uplifting frames of mind towards their activity while an individual who is less satisfied with their jobs holds negative dispositions about the job (Pushpakumari 2008). Job satisfaction is an aftereffect of workers' impression of how well their activity gives those things which are seen as significant. Job satisfaction is likewise characterized as the reintegration of effect created by person's view of satisfaction of his needs in connection to his work and the errands encompassing it (Saiyaden, 2010). Organ and Hammer (2011) called attention to that job satisfaction speaks of complex array of insight, feeling and inclinations. It is the degree to which an employee cherished his work and job activity. Intrinsic factors (recognition, tasks and responsibility) and extrinsic factors (salary, policies, and working condition and company policies) are two set of factors that influence job satisfaction.

Employees who are very committed to their organization ensure a high level of the services' or products' quality, maintenance, productivity and generate higher profits. Employees have more than job satisfaction, are happy that they can serve and are promoters of products and brands. There is evidence that employee involvement increases work performance and overall productivity, creates a better and more productive work environment, reduces employee absence and work leaving (Bin Shmailan 2016). A satisfied employee feels better in the company, perform better his work, but above all feels safe when it comes to his future and work in the enterprise. That is why job satisfaction is such an important element of the work safety (Wolniak and Olkiewicz, 2019; Niciejewska, 2017). The pertinent role that employees play in enhancing organizational performance has seen the subject of employee performance receive massive attention from researchers globally. Each person has different criteria for measuring own job satisfaction. The factor that influences it, is the style of management, but also payments, working hours, schedule, benefits, stress level and flexibility. Job satisfaction is related to productivity, motivation, work performance and life satisfaction (Abuhashesh et al.,2019), which means that this also applies to the private lives of employees. On the other hand, Afshan et al. (2012) define performance as the achievement of specific tasks measured against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. Employee performance can be manifested in improvement in production, easiness in using the new technology, highly motivated workers. For instance, the performance of employees in the banking sector in Karachi is attributed to the frequency and investment in training (Faiza, 2015).

The performance of employees in most companies is directly linked to leadership opportunities, recognition and employee appraisal, meeting employee expectations and socialization are the key factors that motivate employees, managerial standards, motivation, commitment, employee evaluations, positive work environment, technology, incentives, comfort level and nature of management (Ibrahim,2013). Similarly, the performance of employees in Nigeria's firm is tied to the level of motivation of staff. The use of incentives and other motivational strategies is recommended for better performance (Alalade, 2015). The need to build and improve on teamwork and develop leadership to maintain the culture; create opportunities for employees to interact with the managers, improving on the communication; and encouraging employee innovation, increase staff salaries, instituting organizational loyalty programmes and rewarding long-serving employees are key factors that enhance employee performance (Arinanye,2015). The performance of employees in most organizations is also pegged on motivational factors such as salary increment, promotion and recognition. A recommendation to provide services and perform appraisals objectively is diagnosed for improved employee performance (Massudi, 2013).

In Kenya, a study by Sikoro, Namusonge, Makhokha and Nyagechi (2016) reported that job satisfaction among employees of the County government in Kenya is diverse and mainly institution-based. Furthermore, according to Mwangi, Njenga, Chepkilot and Koima (2017), work environment and employee achievement were the critical institutional factors affecting job satisfaction of employees since they fortified a pleasure or positive emotional state in the mobile telecommunication. Further, Chebet (2015) found that the key institutional factors affecting job satisfaction of employees of county governments of Kenya were career advancement, leadership, training and working conditions. Also, Wangechi, Kiragu and Sang (2018) revealed that workplace environment, physical environment and rewards fueled employees' performance and satisfaction with work at the county government of Nyeri.

According to Obwoyere (2016), job satisfaction improved the performance of the employees in Nakuru County. Additionally, Nyamunga (2016) reported that job satisfaction is a critical element that creates a need for employee achievement. Job satisfaction is the amount of overall effect that an employee has toward his/her job; hence, job satisfaction enhances employees' level of activity when under pressure. Kuria (2011) argued that employees are the most satisfied and highly productive when their job offers them security from economic strain, recognition of their effort clean policy of grievances, opportunity to contribute ideas and suggestions, participation in decision making and managing the affairs among others. Ojwang' (2013) asserted that employees who have high in job satisfaction generally love their job, feel that they are being fairly treated and believe that their jobs have many desirable features such as fascinating work, good pay and job security. The employee is an essential element in the process of implementing the enterprise's mission and vision, especially in the production sphere. Employees should meet the performance criteria set by the organization to ensure the quantity and quality of their work. To meet organizational standards, employees need a work environment that allows them to work freely without problems that can stop them from reaching their full potential (Raziq and Maulabakhsh, 2015). They also need appropriate superior that will provide them with this environment, but above all, he will motivate them to work in the right way, make them feel satisfied with their work.

Job satisfaction is increasing in importance, as the competition for talent is high and still growing. It is not hard for a competitor to compete with individual elements of employment such as salaries and benefits. Boyens (2007) focuses on the reasons of involuntary turnover, voluntary turnover, and promotion for employees to leave a particular organization. Furthermore, he says that the two types of turnover are the most devastating for organizations. The effect of voluntary turnover includes loss of performance, knowledge, expertise, relationship, and loss of the time and resources that it took to train the employee. This leads to a feeling of insecurity and affects the performance of the employees who are left because of the constant disruption of services and too much change which as a result affects the general performance of the company. Employee turnover rates have, within the last decade became a nationwide epidemic. Employees in county government no longer feel the sense of company loyalty that once existed. Increasing cases of malpractices by the top management have left employees feeling detached from the companies that they served and haunted by concerns of overall job security. This has led the employees to focus more on job hunting rather than performance thereby hurting the general performance of the organization. With the problem of increasing employee turnover in the counties, one wonders if the goal of the Kenya government concerning the growth and expansion of the counties is going to be realized. Therefore the study sought to determine the effect of employee working condition on organizational performance in the County government of West Pokot.

2. EMPLOYEE WORKING CONDITIONS

Working environment plays an important role towards the employees' performance. Working environment is argued to impact immensely on employees' performance either towards negative or the positive outcomes (Chandrasekar 2001). In the world, there are international organizations who debate the rights of employee. Most people spend fifty percent of their lives within indoor environments, which greatly influence their mental status, actions, abilities and performance (Dorgan, 1994). Better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better workplace environment. Better physical environment of office will boost the employees and ultimately improve their productivity. Various literature pertain to the study of multiple offices and office buildings indicated that the factors such as dissatisfaction, cluttered workplaces and the physical environment are playing a major role in the loss of employees' productivity (Carnevale 1992, Clements- Croome 1997).

Organizations must step outside their traditional roles and comfort zones to look at new ways of working. They have to create a work environment where people enjoy what they do, feel like they have a purpose, have pride in what they do, and can reach their potential. Although working conditions do not have a direct impact on production or output, they indeed have an indirect performance for example if the manual or mental work involved in certain jobs in a factory is tiresome, it will result into endangering not only the company property but also result into accidents which may further involve such incidents like loss of life. This might have adverse effects on the morale of the entire work force. Therefore organizations should establish working conditions that do not affect the work force negatively by providing among other things noise free environments, adequate lighting systems, and adequate temperatures (Hogber 2005).

In the 1990's, the factors of work environment had changed due to the changes in several factors such as the social environment, information technology and the flexible ways of organizing work processes (Hasun & Makhbul, 2005). When employees' are physically and emotionally fit will have the desire to work and their performance outcomes shall be increased. Moreover, a proper workplace environment helps in reducing the number of absenteeism and thus can increase the employees' performance which leads to increased productivity at the workplace (Boles et al. 2004).

Opperman (2002) defines working environment is a composite of three major sub-environments: the technical environment, the human environment and the organizational environment. Technical environment refers to tools, equipment, technological infrastructure and other physical or technical elements. The technical environment creates elements that enable employees perform their respective responsibilities and activities. The human environment refers to peers, others with whom employees relates, team and work groups, interactional issues, the leadership and management. This environment is designed in such a way that encourages informal interaction in the work place so that the opportunity to share knowledge and exchange ideas could be enhanced. This is a basis to attain maximum productivity. Organizational environment include systems, procedures, practices, values and philosophies. Management has control over organizational environment. Measurement system where people are rewarded on quantity, hence workers will have little interest in helping those workers who are trying to improve quality. Thus, issues of organizational environment influence employee's productivity.

Pettersson (2003) states, that in order to manage the work environment, it is very necessary that the organization takes into account the changes which are required and what the company is supposed to do in future. For doing this, the company can check the everyday task and what influence does these tasks have on the work environment. If there are certain examples, which are stressful, then the employees should be provided with temporary relief. An employee who is new to the task or who has been away from work for a long time should be provided with proper information and support to accomplish his/her work. Organizations should also take into consideration, the impact of change, on the employees. Changes like reorganization, introduction of new technologies and change in production have a deep impact on the employees (Pettersson, 2003).

Kingsley (2012) studied on the impact of office ergonomics on employee performance in Ghana National Petroleum Corporation (GNPC). The study aimed at finding out whether the workplace environment of GNPC had any impact on employees' performance. The results showed that deficiencies in office ergonomics affected the performance of employees by varying degrees ranging from 20-80 percent. Leblebici(2012) researched on the impact of workplace quality on employee productivity a case study of a foreign private bank in Turkey. The study was to establish the relationship between the work physical conditions and employee performance. Study showed that employees felt motivated while working in a modernized office, well decorated and well-arranged and with good storage facilities.

Makori, Nandi, Thuo, and Wanyonyi, (2012) a research on influence of occupational health and safety programmers on performance of manufacturing firms in western Kenya. The results showed a positive Pearson correlation of 0.57 and 0.47 which means that there was a moderate positive relation between occupational health and safety programmes and organizations performance. Dwomoh, Owusu, and Addo, (2013) researched on the impact of occupational health and safety policies on employees' performance in Ghana's timber industry. It was evident that health and safety boosts employees' performance, this was attributed to reduced number of absentees as a result of illnesses, improved physical and mental health of an employee.

According to Market Business News (2019), organizational performance involves "analyzing a company's performance against its objectives and goals. In other words, organizational performance comprises real results or outputs compared with intended outputs." It also relates to how successfully an organization performs or achieves their predetermined objectives and goals. The extent of the relationship between job satisfaction and performance has been basically evaluated in different organizational settings. Outcomes of these investigations have not tailored toward one direction. Lee and Chan (1996) have demonstrated that there are connections between job satisfaction and productivity and that the higher the level of satisfaction, the greater the effort to increase productivity. Carroll, Keflas and Watson (2001) found that satisfaction and job productivity are essential relationships in which every influence the other. They recommend that performance prompts more work effort due to high apparent anticipation of rewards or other positive outcomes. The exertion prompts powerful presentation, which again prompts fulfillment in urgent relationship.

Naseem, (2011) examined the relationship between employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction and the impact of both on the success of organization among hotels in Pakistan. It was viewed that the satisfied employees would culminate customer satisfaction. Data collected was subjected to the principal component analysis which revealed that great deal of employees' satisfaction among the surveyed cohorts where customers also had expressed satisfaction with the existing services. The customers were satisfied mainly with the environmental cleanliness, quality food and room services while the employees were satisfied with the conducive working environment with salary and frequent trainings which enabled the employees to work with dedication to uplift their organization which was clearly reflected by the satisfaction level of customers. The study thus establishes an indirect relationship between employee satisfaction and organizational success which was mediated by the customers.

Job satisfaction is very essential as it has many positive organizational outcomes, as well as vital positive outcomes to individual employees. As Cranny et al (1992) note, Job satisfaction creates positive high staff morale among employees. When an employee is dissatisfied, he directly or indirectly spread his dissatisfaction to the rest of the staff. This can cause a heavy decrease in the morale of the entire staff and can bring about a heavy decrease in productivity. In fact, a dissatisfied and unmotivated employee is a serious threat to the well-being of any organization. Job satisfaction increases an employee commitment to an organization. An employee who is satisfied will want to remain in the job to give his best to his employing organization, whereas an unsatisfied employee will always be on the look-out for another job, and will leave the organization at any slight chance or opportunity. Additionally, job satisfaction improves the intensity of motivation among employees,

as well as enhances the quality of the job and productivity level of employees (Ahmad et al., 2012; Seema & Maryam, 2013; Aaron et al., 2015). According to Noe et al. (2003), satisfied workers are more eager and willing to apply new knowledge and innovation to their job performance and this always help organizations develop good competitive advantages in business arena. Job satisfaction also serves as a strong strategy for recruiting great worker. This is because, employees who are satisfy with their total job facets in an organization will attempt to recruit people they know who have the skills and competencies necessary to help the company. Moreover, when existing staffs speak favourably and positively about their organization, these verbal make prospective employees see the organization as a destiny of choice. This helps to attract talented and experienced individuals to their organizations. Additionally, job satisfaction creates favourable employee attitudes that are associated with lower rates of personal turnover and less absenteeism.

Kasim and Ghaffar (2012) note that job satisfaction generate loyalty, self-confidence and high commitment to the organization and also lead to productivity improvement and eliminations of organizational deviant behaviors, as well as absenteeism and turnover (Linda & Michael, 2014). Thus job satisfaction helps to motivate employees and improve their commitment to the organization. Numerous research studies have been conducted on the relationship between employee performance and job satisfaction, most of the studies believe that job satisfaction is directly linked with employees' desire and willingness to stay with their organizations (Johnson, 2004, Perez, 2008, Sutherland, 2004). Most studies assume that employee retention strategies can affect job satisfaction; therefore, organizations that need to retain their employees need to adopt policies and practices that lead to satisfaction on the job. (Ahmed *et al.* 2009, Ongori&Agolla, 2009, Somaya& Williamson, 2008). Memon, Panhwar, and Rohra (2010), in their analysis suggest that employees who are satisfied with their jobs are less likely to leave. Job satisfaction involves employees feeling valued by their organizations for their contributions and accomplishments, being able to take decisions that affect their job role and performance, having opportunities to grow in their career, having a flexible work schedule, working in a friendly and pleasant work environment and having good relationship with their leaders and colleagues (Branham, 2005).

Stoner, Freeman and Gilbert (2007) affirm that "managers and management researchers have long believed that organizational goals are unattainable without the enduring commitment of members of the organization". There will be no improvement on employees' performance without employees being motivated to perform. Several authors have given many definitions to motivation. However, a general understanding from the various definitions of Motivation is that motivation is what causes one to act (Stoner et al, 2007). It is the process that guides and maintains goal-oriented behavior.

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design with a target population 1000 workers within the county government of West Pokot, Kenya. Data collection instrument included questionnaire and other information relevant to the study. A structured questionnaire was administered to the respondents. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of data collection instrument. The data will be reduced, organized, coded, edited, classified using a table and analyzed to bring out the meaning under each of the factors. It was then be coded, entered and analyzed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSION

Working environment plays an important role towards the employees 'performance. Working environment is argued to impact immensely on employees' performance either towards negative or the positive outcomes (Chandrasekar2001). In the world, there are international organizations who debate the rights of employee. Most people spend fifty percent of their lives within indoor environments, which greatly influence their mental status, actions, abilities and performance (Dorgan, 1994). Better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better workplace environment. Better physical environment of office will boosts the employees and ultimately improve their productivity. The study sought to determine the effect of employee working condition on organizational performance in the county government of West Pokot. The findings are presented in a five point Likerts scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

Table 4.1 below contains a summary of data relating to attitude of respondents towards determining the effect of working condition on organizational performance of the county government of West Pokot. In particular, when respondents were

asked whether working environment plays an important role towards the employees 'performance. The distribution of findings showed that 46.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed to the statement that working environment plays an important role towards the employees 'performance, 27.0 percent of them agreed, 1.0 percent of the respondents were neutral, 12.0 percent disagreed while 14.0 percent of them strongly disagreed. These findings implied that working environment plays an important role towards the employees 'performance. The respondents were also asked whether better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better workplace environment. The distribution of the responses indicated that 25.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement that better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better workplace environment. 30.0 percent of them agreed, and 6.0 percent of them were neutral, 33.0 percent of them disagreed while 6.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better workplace environment.

The respondents were also asked whether better physical environment of office will boosts the employees and ultimately improve their productivity. The distribution of the responses indicated that 24.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 28.0 percent of them agreed, and 5.0 percent of them were neutral, 26.0 percent of them disagreed while 17.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that better physical environment of office will boosts the employees and ultimately improve their productivity. The respondents were further asked whether there is provision of noise free environments, adequate lighting systems, and adequate temperatures. The distribution of the responses indicated that 33.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 25.0 percent of them agreed, 5.0 percent of them were neutral while 20.0 percent and 17.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that there is provision of noise free environments, adequate lighting systems, and adequate temperatures

The respondents were further asked whether organizations can prevent accidents and maintain good safety records through development of a positive safety culture to ensure good working condition hence performance improvement. The distribution of the responses indicated that 21.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 36.0 percent of them agreed, 4.0 percent of them were neutral, 21.0 percent of them disagreed while 18.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that organizations can prevent accidents and maintain good safety records through development of a positive safety culture to ensure good working condition hence performance improvement. The respondents were asked whether good employee working environment enhances organisation performance. The distribution of the responses indicated that 22.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 28.0 percent of them agreed, 4.0 percent of them were neutral, another 27.0 percent of them disagreed while 19.0 of them strongly disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that good employee working environment enhances organisation performance.

Table 4.1: Effect of Employee Working Condition on Organizational Performance in the County Government of West Pokot

statements		SA	A	N	D	SD	T
Working environment plays an important role towards the employees 'performance	%	46.0	27.0	1.0	12.0	14.0	100
Better outcomes and increased productivity is assumed to be the result of better workplace environment	%	25.0	30.0	6.0	33.0	6.0	100
Better physical environment of office will boosts the employees and ultimately improve their productivity	%	24.0	28.0	5.0	26.0	17.0	100
There is provision of noise free environments, adequate lighting systems, adequate temperatures	%	33.0	25.0	5.0	20.0	17.0	100
Organizations can prevent accidents and maintain good safety records through development of a positive safety culture to ensure good working condition hence performance improvement	%	21.0	36.0	4.0	21.0	18.0	100
Good employee working environment enhances organisation performance	%	22.0	28.0	4.0	27.0	19.0	100

4.1 Inferential Statistics

4.1.1 Pearson Correlation

The study sought to establish the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study. Pearson correlation coefficient was computed at 95 percent confidence interval (error margin of 0.05). Table 4.2 illustrates the findings of the study.

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

		Organizational performance
Employee working condition	Pearson Correlation	.612**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	49

As shown on Table 4.2 above, the p-value for employee working condition was found to be 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.612, which represented an average, positive relationship between employee working conditions on organizational performance in the county government of West Pokot.

4.1.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regressions were computed at 95 percent confidence interval (0.05 margin error) to show the multiple linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

4.1.2.1 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 4.3 shows that the coefficient of correlation (R) is positive 0.476. This means that there is a positive correlation between the effects of employee job satisfaction on organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. The coefficient of determination (R Square) indicates that 22.6% of organizational performance in county government of West Pokot is influenced by employee job satisfaction. The adjusted R^2 however, indicates that 18.5% of employee job satisfaction is influenced by the organizational performance in county government of West Pokot leaving 81.5% to be influenced by other factors that were not captured in this study.

Table 4.3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.476 ^a	.226	.185	.90429350

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Working Condition

4.1.2.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4.4 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The p-value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting employee job satisfaction affect organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. The results also indicate that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable. The ANOVA results indicate that the independent variables significantly ($F=5.445$, $P=0.000$) explain the variance of organizational performance in county government of West Pokot.

Table 4.4: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	215.264	1	4.451	6.423	.000 ^b
1 Residual	77.050	48	.822		
Total	292.314	49			

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance in County Government of West Pokot

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Working Condition

4.1.2.3 Regression Coefficients

From the Coefficients table (Table 4.5) the regression model can be derived as follows:

$$Y = 0.009 + 0.664X_1$$

The results in table 4.5 indicate that all the independent variables have a significant positive effect on organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. The most influential variable is employee working condition with a regression coefficient of 0.664 (p-value = 0.000). According to this model when all the independent variables values are zero; organizational performance in county government of West Pokot of will have a score of 0.009.

Table 4.5: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error				Beta
1						
	(Constant)	.009	.095		.019	.000
	Employee working condition	.664	.093	.157	1.551	.000

a. Dependent Variable: organizational performance in county government of West Pokot

4.1.3 Hypotheses Testing

4.1.3.1 Hypothesis One

H0₁: Employee working condition does not have a significant effect on organizational performance in county government of West Pokot.

From Table 4.5 above, employee working condition ($\beta = .664$) was found to be positively related organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. From t-test analysis, the t -value was found to be 1.551 and the ρ -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $\rho < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that employee working condition has a significant effect on organizational performance in county government of West Pokot.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion basing on the findings, employee working condition ($\beta = .664$) was found to be positively related organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. From t-test analysis, the t -value was found to be 1.551 and the ρ -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $\rho < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that employee working condition has a significant effect on organizational performance in county government of West Pokot. The study came up with a number of recommendations. The study recommends that the management of county government of West Pokot should provide a healthy safe and conducive working condition to enable employees boost their moral towards the ultimate improvement of their productivity work towards the achievement of the organizational goals. The management of county government of West Pokot should seek guidance of terms and conditions to provide proper job and the assurance of its continuance in future as well as the absence of threatening factors and that short term employment results in: unscheduled turnover, low staff morale, and low productivity.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aaron, D.A., Anusorn, S. & Vivian, T. (2015). Consumers as employees: the impact of social responsibility on quality of work life among Australian engineers. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 11 (1), 98 – 108 Ahmad,
- [2] Abuhashesh, M., Al-Dmour, R., Masa'deh, R., 2019. Factors that affect Employees Job Satisfaction and Performance to Increase Customers' Satisfactions, *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 23, Article ID 354277, DOI: 10.5171/2019.354277.
- [3] Adamu, S. (2008), *Manpower Planning and Administration*, Lagos: National Open University of Nigeria.
- [4] Afshan & Elbert, N.F. (2012). *Performance Management*. Columbus: Merrill Publishing Company

- [5] Alalade, (2015), Effect of job satisfaction on employee performance. *Journal of business management*.
- [6] Alam GM, Hoque KE, Ismail L, Mishra PK (2010). DO developing countries need education laws to manage its system or are ethics and a market-driven approach sufficient? *6858 Afr. J. Bus. Manage.*, 4(15): 3406-3416
- [7] Alam GM (2009). The role of science and technology education at network age population for sustainable development of Bangladesh through human resource advancement. *Sci. Res. Essays*, 4(11): 1260-1270
- [8] Akinbobola, O.I. (2011), Conflict in Human Capital Relationships: The Impact of Job Satisfaction on Job Involvement in a Workplace, *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 1(2): 92-95.
- [9] Armstrong, M. (1996), *A Handbook on Personnel Management Practice*, (5th edition), London: Kogan Page.
- [10] Aronson, K.R.; Laurenceau, J.P.; Sieveking, N. & Bellet, W. (2005), Job Satisfaction as a Function of Job Level, *Administration Policy Mental Health*, 32(3): 285-291.
- [11] Ayodo, I. A., Namusonge, G. S., Ayodo, K. & Maluti, V. (2014) Influence of Training on Employee Retention in Public Universities in Kenya: Case of the Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology-Kenya. *International Journal for Management Science and Technology*, 2(4).
- [12] Aziri, B., (2011). Job satisfaction: a literature review, *Management Research And Practice*, 3(4), 77-86.
- [13] Barry, G., Harvey, B.M, & Ray, N.O. (2015). Employee Compensation: Theory, Practice, and Evidence. *Working Paper*
- [14] Bin Shmailan, A.S., 2016. The relationship between job satisfaction, job performance and employee engagement: An explorative study, *Issues in Business Management and Economics*, *J.Bus. Management* 4(1), 1-8, DOI:10.15739/IBME.16.001.
- [15] Brannigan, A. and Zwerman, W. (2001), The Real Hawthorne Effect, *Society*, 38(2):55.
- [16] Baridam, D. M. and Nwibere, B.M. (2008). *Understanding and managing organizational behavior*. Port Harcourt: Sherbrook Associates
- [17] Banfield, P., & Kay, R. (2008). *Introduction to human resource management*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [18] Boyens (2007), Involuntary and Voluntary Employee Turnover, *J.Human Resource Management*
- [19] Buchanan, K. (2011). Job Performance and Satisfaction: Retrieved from: [http://ezinearticles.com /? Job_Performance_and_Satisfaction &id=290072](http://ezinearticles.com/?Job_Performance_and_Satisfaction&id=290072).
- [20] Caroline, M. & Kanyanjua, D. (2019). Determinants of Employee Performance in Manufacturing Firms in Kenya: A Case Study of the East African Portland Cement Company, *Journal of Human Resource & Leadership*, 3(3), 79-94
- [21] Chukwunenye, I.O., & Igbokwe, B.N. (2011), Training, manpower development and job performance: perception and relevance among civil servants in Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 3(6), 399-406, <http://www.academicjournals.org/JEIF> [accessed 3 September 2018].
- [22] Cranny, C. J.; Smith, P. C. & Stone, E. F. (1992), *Job Satisfaction*, Lexington Books: New York.
- [23] Creswell, J.& Clark, M.(2017. *Research Design; Qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. (4th Ed), Washington DC, Sage Publications, Inc.
- [24] Daneshfard, C. & Ekvaniyan, K.E. (2012), Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction in Islamic Azad University, *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*,3(9):168-181.
- [25] Eyupoglu, S.Z. & Saner, T. (2009), Job Satisfaction: Does Rank Make a Difference?, *African Journal of Business Management*, 3(10): 609-615.
- [26] Folami, L. & Bline, D. (2012), Relationship among Job Satisfaction, Task Complexity, and Organizational Context in Public Accounting, *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 8(4): 207-224.

- [27] Gerhart, B., Milkovich, G. T., & Murray, B. (2010). Pay, performance, and participation. *J. human resource management*
- [28] Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnely, (1997), *Organizational Performance USA*, Irwin McGraw-Hill, p-109.
- [29] H. A. R., Jafar, A.A., Zainab, A., Khulood, B., Eman, A.R., Asia, A.S. & Erika, S. F. (2012). Jordanian nurses' job satisfaction and intention to quit. *J. Leadership in Health Services*, 25 (3), 216-231
- [30] Hunjra AI, Chani MI, Sher A, Azam M, Kashif-Ur-Rehman (2010). Factors effecting job satisfaction of employees in Pakistani banking sector. *Afr. J. Bus. Manag.*, 4(10): 2157-2163
- [31] Jain, S.; Sharma, S. & Jain, R. (2011), Job Satisfaction in Banking: A Study of Private and Public Sector Banks (Comparative Study), *International Journal of Science & Technology*, 2(1): 40-48.
- [32] Jamal Nazrul Islam, Haradhan Kumar Mohajan, Rajib Datta,(2012). Organizational performance. *Int. J. Eco. Res.*, 2012, 153-173 ISSN: 2229-6158 IJER | Jul - Aug 2012 Available online@www.ijeronline.com 171
- [33] Karl & Sutton (1998), Job Values in Today's Workforce: A Comparison of Public and Private Sector Employees, *Public Personnel Management*, 27: 515-528.
- [34] Khan, R.A.G., Khan, F.A. & Khan, M.A. (July, 2011), Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance, *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 11(7). *Global Journals Inc.* (USA).
- [35] Lewin, O. Mitchell, & P. Sherer (Eds.), *Research Frontiers in Industrial Relations*, pp. 193-238. Madison, WI: *Industrial Relations Research Association*.
- [36] Market Business News (2019). Organizational performance: definition and meaning. Retrieved from: <https://marketbusinessnews.com/financial>
- [37] Maurice, A. (1998), Happy Workers Miss Fewer Days: Study, *National Underwriter/Property & Casualty Risk & Benefits*, 102: 13-18.
- [38] McDonald, B.D. & Hutcheson, D. (1999), Employee Loyalty, Commitment Directly Impact the Bottom Line, *Business Press*, 11: 18-27.
- [39] Kazmi A (2011). Doctors strike-A result of rage or corruption? Retrieved on July 09, 2016.
- [40] Koys, D. J. (2001). The effects of employee satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior, and turnover on organizational effectiveness: A unit-level, longitudinal study. *Personnel psychology*, 54(1), 101-114.
- [41] Nguyen A, Taylor J, Bradley S (2003). Relative Pay and Job Satisfaction. Some New Evidence, *MPRA Paper No 1382*.
- [42] Nwachukwu, C. C. (2006). *Management: Theory and Practice*. Onitsha: Africana Feb. Publishers.
- [43] Obiekwe Onyebuchi PhD, Obibhunun Lucky(2019), Impact of Employee Job Satisfaction on Organizational Performance, *Academic Journal of Current Research*: Vol. 6 No. 12: December
- [44] Okpara J.O (2004). Personal characteristics as predictors of job satisfaction. An exploratory study of IT managers in a developing economy. *Inform. Technol. People*, 17(3): 327-338.
- [45] Olalere, T.O. & Adesoji, A.A. (2013), Human Capital Development in First Bank of Nigeria Plc, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science* 4(2). MCSER-CEMAS-Sapienza University of Rome.
- [46] Omollo, (2015). Organizational performance. *J. Bus. management*
- [47] Organ, D.W. & Hammer, W.C. (2011). *Organization behaviour: An applied psychological approach*. Texas: Business Publication.
- [48] Opkara JO (2002). The Impact of Salary Differential on Managerial Job Satisfaction. A Study of the Gender Gap And Its Implications For Management Education And Practice In A Developing Economy. *J. Bus. Dev. Nation*, 65-92.

- [49] Ozer G, Gunluk M (2010). The effects of discrimination perception and job satisfaction on Turkish public accountants' turnover intention. *Afr. J. Bus. Manag.*, 4(8): 1500-1509.
- [50] Part F (1999). The relationship between job satisfaction and performance of boys in secondary schools of Torghabeh district, *M.A. thesis*, Ferdousi Mashhad University, Iran.
- [51] Padilla-Velez D (1993). *Job satisfaction of vocational teachers in Puerto Rico*. The Ohio State University
- [52] Park HJ, Mitsuhashi H, Fey CF, Bjorkman I (2003). The effect of human resource management practices on Japanese MNC subsidiary performance. A practical mediating model. *Int. J. Hum. Res. Manage.*, 14(8): 1391-1406.
- [53] Plamínek, J. (2010). *Effective Appraisal tool*. Praha: Grada Publishing.
- [54] Pushpakumari, M. D. (2008). The impact of job satisfaction on job performance: An empirical analysis. Retrieved from: [http://202.11.2.2113/SEBM/ronso/n09_1/0Richard & Robbins, P.S. \(2001\). Organizational behaviour. India: Pearson Education, Inc.](http://202.11.2.2113/SEBM/ronso/n09_1/0Richard%20&%20Robbins,%20P.S.%20(2001).%20Organizational%20behaviour.%20India:%20Pearson%20Education,%20Inc.)
- [55] Raziq, A., Maulabakhsh, R. 2015. Impact of Working Environment on Job Satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23, 717-725, DOI: 10.1016/S2212- 5671(15)00524-9.
- [56] Saiyaden, M.A. (2010). *Human resources management*. New Delhi: McGraw-Hill.
- [57] Sokoya SK (2000). Personal Predictors of Job Satisfaction for the Public Sector Manager. Implications for Management Practice and Development in a Developing Economy. *J. Business in Developing Nations*, available at www.rh.edu/Ismt/jbdnv40.htm.
- [58] Wolniak, R., Olkiewicz, M., (2019). The Relations between Safety Culture and Quality Culture, *System Safety: Human - Technical Facility - Environment*, 1(1), 10-17, DOI: 10.2478/czoto-2019-0002.